

Synthesis and Biological Activity of Pyrido[3',2' : 4,5]thieno[3,2-d]pyrimidines

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2-Carboethoxy-3-aminothieno[2,3-b]pyridines (1) were reacted with isothiocyanates to obtain 2-thio-3-substituted-7,9-diphenylpyrido[3',2' : 4,5]thieno[3,2-d]pyrimidin-4(3H)-ones (3) which on methylation afforded 2-methylmercapto-3-substituted-7,9-diphenylpyrido[3',2' : 4,5]thieno[3,2-d]pyrimidin-4(3H)-ones (4). Interesting profile of analgesic and antiinflammatory activity has been observed during preliminary screening of the compounds (3,4).

PYRIDOTHIENOPYRIMIDINES, an example of triheterocyclic system, have attracted much attention because of their promising biological activities¹. Moreover, the literature survey revealed that no study has been undertaken for the reaction between 2-carboethoxy-3-aminothieno[2,3-b]pyridines and various isothiocyanates. Therefore, several pyrido[3',2' : 4,5]thieno[3,2-d]pyrimidin-4(3H)-ones (3, 4) have been synthesised and screened for analgesic and antiinflammatory activities.

When compounds 1 were refluxed for several hours with various isothiocyanates (RNCS) in pyridine, compounds 3 were obtained. 3 were methylated at position-2 by dimethyl sulphate in basic medium to yield 4 (Chart 1). Attempts to isolate the intermediate thiourea derivatives from the reaction between 1 and isothiocyanates met with failures, when these were refluxed in ethanol, dioxane, *N,N*-dimethyl formamide, ethanol saturated with dry HCl gas, sodium ethoxide and NaOH separately. Either the starting material or a mixture was recovered (tlc). Formation of the cyclic compound 3 was proved on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral data.

Chart 1

Ir (KBr) spectra of 3 showed bands at 3 370–3 360 (NH), 1 690 (C=O), 1 545 and 1 360 (NHCS) and 1 200 cm^{-1} (C=S). Compounds 4 exhibited C=O absorption near 1 680 cm^{-1} . Absence of bands due to C=S and NH suggested methylation at position-2 of compounds 3. No signal for CH_2CH_3 protons appeared in any of the compounds (3) in their ¹H nmr spectra, which obviously ruled out any possibility of the formation of intermediate thiourea derivatives (2). A singlet at δ 8.20–8.35 (NH) integrating for one proton in compounds 3, was found to be absent in compounds 4, and a singlet integrating for three protons (SCH_3) present at δ 1.75–1.96 claimed S-methylation of compounds 3 (Table 1).

Mass spectrum of 3b exhibited a strong molecular ion peak at m/z 463 which represents also the base peak. The fragment ion $[M - \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NCS}]^+$ is typical for fused pyrimidines with thione functionality² (Chart 2).

Chart 2

Biological activity : Analgesic activity of 3 and 4 was determined by chemical writhing test in mice³ with aspirin as the standard. Except 3g, 3h and 4a, all the compounds exhibited analgesic activity. Compounds 3b, 4b and 4g were the most potent. Results suggested that methylation at position-2 enhanced the activity.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF PYRIDOTHIENOPYRIMIDINES (3, 4)*

Compd. no.	R	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Analyses % : Found/(Calcd.)			δ (ppm)
					O	H	N	
3a	n-C ₄ H ₉	58	243-44	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	67.72 (67.69)	4.58 (4.77)	9.05 (9.47)	0.98 (8H, t, CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.04-1.96 (4H, m, -CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 4.49 (2H, t, CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 7.53-8.18 (11H, m, ArH), 8.20 (1H, s, NH) 7.18-8.21 (16H, m, ArH), 8.30 (1H, NH)
3b	C ₆ H ₅	42	318-20	C ₂₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	70.19 (69.95)	8.92 (8.70)	9.90 (9.06)	7.18-8.21 (16H, m, ArH), 8.30 (1H, NH)
3c	2-OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	66	302-04	C ₂₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	70.93 (70.42)	8.89 (4.01)	8.58 (8.80)	2.45 (8H, s, 2-CH ₃), 7.12-8.30 (15H, m, ArH), 8.35 (1H, s, NH)
3d	3-OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	41	311-18	C ₂₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	70.74	4.40	8.91	2.42 (8H, s, 3-CH ₃), 7.07-8.22 (15H, m, ArH), 8.34 (1H, s, NH)
3e	4-OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	53	300-02	C ₂₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	70.69	4.39	8.68	2.39 (8H, s, 4-CH ₃), 7.18-8.40 (15H, m, ArH), 8.35 (1H, s, NH)
3f	2-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	50	245-46	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	67.97 (68.18)	8.64 (8.88)	8.77 (8.51)	—
3g	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	41	327-28	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	68.35	8.98	8.88	—
3h	3-ClC ₆ H ₄	55	329-30	C ₂₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	65.46 (65.12)	8.49 (8.24)	8.08 (8.44)	—
4a	n-C ₄ H ₉	92	247-48	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	68.08 (68.24)	5.41 (5.07)	9.47 (9.18)	0.94 (8H, t, CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.15- 1.73 (4H, m, -CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 8.9 (2H, t, CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.8 (8H, s, SOCH ₃), 7.15-8.6 (15H, m, ArH)
4b	C ₆ H ₅	70	380-82	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	70.11 (70.42)	8.91 (9.01)	8.62 (8.80)	1.75 (8H, s, SOCH ₃), 7.32-8.28 (16H, m, ArH)
4c	1-OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	61	266-68	C ₂₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	70.49 (70.85)	4.60 (4.81)	8.44 (8.55)	1.82 (8H, s, SOCH ₃), 2.45 (8H, s, 2-CH ₃), 7.20-8.30 (15H, m, ArH)
4d	3-OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	78	321-23	C ₂₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	70.51	4.58	8.30	1.78 (8H, s, SOCH ₃), 2.40 (8H, s, 3-CH ₃), 7.20-8.30 (15H, m, ArH)
4e	4-OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	68	279-81	C ₂₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	70.48	4.49	8.31	1.85 (8H, s, SOCH ₃), 2.11 (8H, s, 4-CH ₃), 7.35-8.31 (15H, m, ArH)
4f	2-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	71	245-46	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	68.97 (68.62)	4.42 (4.17)	8.50 (8.28)	1.96 (8H, s, SOCH ₃), 3.77 (8H, s, 2-OCH ₃), 7.03-8.23 (15H, m, ArH)
4g	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	68	249-51	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	68.80	4.49	8.54	1.92 (8H, s, SOCH ₃), 3.80 (8H, s, 4-OCH ₃), 7.00-8.22 (15H, m, ArH)
4h	3-ClC ₆ H ₄	92	301-02	C ₂₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	65.93 (65.68)	3.51 (3.54)	8.02 (8.21)	1.83 (8H, s, SOCH ₃), 7.30-8.30 (15H, m, ArH)

*Compounds (3 and 4) were crystallised from EtOH+DMF; ¹H nmr spectra of 3 and 4 were run in TFA and CDCl₃ respectively.

Antiinflammatory activity (3 and 4g) was performed by rat paw oedema method⁴ with indomethacin as the standard. Results suggested that all the compounds displayed promising activity. Special notice has been made to 3f and 3g with the excellent activity, which is equal to or a little greater than that of indomethacin.

Experimental

M.p.s. were taken in open capillaries using a Toshniwal melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were run on Perkin-Elmer IR-397 and IR-180 spectrophotometers, ¹H nmr (TFA, CDCl₃) spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R 12B, 60 MHz instrument downfield from TMS and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-D 300 instrument. Purity of compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel-G plates and iodine was used to reveal the spots.

2-Thioxo-3-substituted-7,9-diphenylpyrido[3',2':4,5]thieno[3,2-d]pyrimidin-4(3H)-ones (3): A mixture of 2-carbomethoxy-3-amino-4,6-diphenylthieno[2,3-b]pyridine⁵ (1; 0.01 mol) and appropriate isothio-

cyanate (0.01 mol) in pyridine (25.0 ml) was refluxed in an oil-bath for 30-35 h (tlc). The reaction mixture was then cooled and triturated with aqueous ethanol. The resulting solid was filtered, dried and crystallised from EtOH-DMF mixture.

2-Methylmercapto-3-substituted-7,9-diphenylpyrido[3',2':4,5]thieno[3,2-d]pyrimidin-4(3H)-ones (4): A mixture of 3 (0.02 mol), NaOH (1N; 15.0 ml) and ethanol (40.0 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath. To the clear solution thus obtained, was added dropwise dimethyl sulphate (0.02 mol, 2.52 g) in ethanol (20.0 ml) with stirring. The reaction mixture was then further refluxed for 30 min, cooled and poured to ice-cold water. The resulting solid was filtered, dried and crystallised from EtOH-DMF mixture.

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